

POST-COVID-19 ECONOMIC STABILITY CHANGES IN NINE COUNTRIES OF ASIA PACIFIC ECONOMIC COOPERATION

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Abstract

This study examines changes in economic stability after Covid-19 and the impact of Covid-19 causing an economic recession in all countries, especially in 9 countries (Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Mexico, Chile, and Peru). Where the variables are fiscal policy or crowding out (government spending and investment), monetary policy or time lag (exchange rate), and economic stability (economic growth and inflation). This study uses secondary data or time-series from 2010 to 2019. Model in this study is the ARDL Panel viewed from the sharp edge with IRF analysis, FEVD, and Panel ARDL. The results of the FEVD analysis show as operational targets. Then the results of the AEDL Panel analysis show that the Panel on inflation, investment, and government spending can control economic stability, precisely at the level of economic growth in 9 countries both in the short and long term.

Keywords: Economic Stability, Covid-19 and especially in 9 countries.

I. INTRODUCTION

The inward looking strategy is based on the idea that a high rate of economic growth can be achieved by developing domestic industries that produce imported substitutes (Tambunan, 2001), (Bartik et al, 2020), (Coibon et al, 2020), (Dietrich et all 2022) (Hüseysin en, A. K., 2020). In addition, according to Aydin, Esen and Bayrak (2016). An increase in inflation will generally reduce people's purchasing power (Cavallo et all, 2017) (Dietrich et all 2022) (Cavallo et all, 2020). The increase in the prices of goods and services due to the dynamics of inflation will make people suffocate with the large consumption costs that must be incurred (Armantier et all, 2020) (Baker et all, 2020a) (Baker et all 2020b).

Table 1. Foreign Direct Investment Rate

Periode	Bulan	Indonesia	Jepang	Malaysia	Filiphina	Singapura	Thailand	Mexico	Chile	Peru
Sebelum Covid-19	Januari	0.99	0.37	3.01	1.83	21.23	3.06	2.27	1.95	1.34
	April	2.54	1.16	6.18	2.30	26.54	0.49	4.34	3.19	4.11
	Juli	2.66	0.48	0.71	1.81	29.05	1.59	1.84	5.59	3.74
	Oktober	2.01	0.57	0.64	1.71	28.38	3.24	2.09	5.75	2.41
Sesudah Covid-19	Januari	1.59	0.71	2.52	2.26	29.37	-0.59	1.17	2.33	5.12
	April	1.70	0.16	1.40	1.74	17.04	2.13	1.25	9.45	1.96
	Juli	1.85	4.06	0.05	1.62	26.18	-0.19	1.50	3.41	0.57
	Oktober	1.45	0.74	1.72	2.28	18.39	-0.03	0.01	1.70	0.01

Source: Ceicdata

Based on the table above, we can see in the Nine Countries Of Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation, that investment experienced extraordinary fluctuations due to the covid 19 tragedy. Seen at the end of 2019 to early 2020 in October in Indonesia, investment was 2.01% increased and in January investment fell by 1.59%, then in October in Japan investment fell by 0.57% and in January investment rose by 0.71%. In Malaysia, investment in October decreased by 0.64% and in January investment increased by 2.52%, then in the Philippines, investment decreased by 1.71% in October and then in January investment increased by 2.26%. In Singapore, investment in October fell by 28.38%, and in January investment increased by 29.37%, then in Thailand investment in October increased by 3.24% and in January decreased by -0.59%, in Mexico in the month of October. October investment increased by 2.09% and in January investment decreased by 1.17%, then in Chile investment in October increased by 5.75% and in January investment decreased by 2.33%. In Peru, investment in October decreased by 2.41% and in January investment increased by 5.12%. The economic recession has an impact on the decline in various macroeconomic sources such as investment, weakening exchange rates, and declining exports (Baker et al, 2020) (Bodamaev et al, 2020) (World Bank, 2021). In particular, in poor and developing countries.

Figure: 1.1 Level of Direct Investment (Nine Country Of Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation) Period 2010 to 2019

Based on the graph above, we can see in the Nine Countries of Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation that investment fluctuates. The investment figure in Indonesia in 2011 increased by 11,528 billion US\$ and in 2010 investment decreased by 11,106 billion US\$, but investment in 2019 increased by 20,053 billion US\$. The investment figure in Japan in 2016 increased by 137,656 billion US\$ and in 2015 investment decreased by 133,163 billion US\$, but investment in 2019 increased by 215,276 billion US\$. Malaysia's investment figure in 2012 increased by 8,001 billion US\$, but in the following year from 2013 to 2019 investment experienced a very drastic decline of 1,392 billion US\$. The Philippines' investment figure in 2017 increased by 6,952 billion US\$ and in 2016 investment decreased by 5,883 billion US\$, but investment in

2019 decreased by 4,376 billion US\$. Singapore's investment figure in 2015 increased by 24,551 billion US\$ and in 2014 investment decreased by 16,221 billion US\$, but in 2019 investment increased by 72,182 billion US\$. Thailand's investment figure in 2017 decreased by 5,932 billion US\$ and in 2016 it increased by 9,906 billion US\$, but in 2019 investment decreased by 5,328 billion US\$. Mexico's investment figure in 2013 increased by 32,758 billion US\$ and in the following year from 2014 to 2019 investment experienced a very drastic decline of 23,231 billion US\$. Chile's investment figure in 2013 increased by 12,322 billion US\$ and in the following year from 2014 to 2019 investment decreased drastically by 3.5 billion US\$. Peru's investment figure in 2012 increased by 11,867 billion US\$ until 2019 investment decreased by 7,996 billion US\$.

Table 1.2: (GDP: Real GDP Growth) Before and After Covid 19 (Nine Country Of Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation) Period 2019 to 2020

period	Month	Indonesia	Japan	Malaysia	Filiphina	Singapore	Thailand	Mexico	Chile	Peru
Before Covid-19	Januari	5.17	0.30	4.77	6.29	1.10	3.71	1.19	3.01	4.64
	April	5.06	0.83	4.54	6.21	1.01	2.89	0.07	1.86	2.47
	July	5.05	0.86	4.77	5.14	0.20	2.45	0.02	1.84	1.19
	October	5.02	1.74	4.39	6.13	0.70	2.64	0.46	2.80	3.23
After Covid-19	Januari	4.96	-0.66	3.55	6.68	1.01	1.46	-0.78	-2.39	1.85
	April	2.96	1.92	0.73	-0.63	-2.01	-1.98	-2.12	0.42	-3.46
	July	-5.32	-1.02	-1.71	1.65	-1.34	-1.13	-1.67	-1.01	-2.78
	October	1.44	-0.39	-1.47	2.48	-2.22	-0.49	-4.08	2.94	1.98

Source: Ceicdata

Based on the graph above, we can see in (Nine Country Of Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation), that GDP experienced extraordinary fluctuations due to the Covid-19 tragedy. Seen at the end of 2019 to the beginning of 2020 in Indonesia the GDP in October of 5.02 billion increased and decreased in January by 4.96 billion, then in Japan in October the GDP of 1.74 billion experienced an increase and in January the GDP decreased of -0.66 billion, in Malaysia the GDP in October increased by 4.39 billion and decreased in January by 3.55 billion. In the Philippines, GDP decreased by 6.13 billion in October and in January, GDP increased by 6.68 billion, then in Singapore, GDP decreased by 0.70 billion in October and in January, GDP increased by 1.01 billion, then Thailand's GDP in October experienced an increase of 2.64 billion, and decreased in January by 1.46 billion, then in Mexico the GDP in October increased by 0.46 billion, and decreased in January by -0.78 billion, followed by Chile's GDP in October of 2.80 billion experienced an increase and GDP decreased in January by -2.39 billion, in Peru the GDP in October increased by 3.23 billion, and decreased in January by 1.85 billion. Since its emergence in December 2019, the Covid-19 pandemic has had a very serious impact on almost all aspects of human life on earth, especially in the economic sector (Bodea et al, 2021) (Carvalho et al, 2020) (Al Refai et al, 2012). 2022). Based on these problems, researchers have an interest in researching what are the impacts of Covid-19 on the economy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dynamic Rational Expectation Analysis

Changes in the supply of gold and demand for the stock of gold coins will change the price of the balance of PG/P. In the dynamic gold standard model, it is easier to use rational expectations if the gold standard model is in linear form. For example, inflation expectations, general price level gold stock and non-monetary gold stock The demand model for gold and non-monetary money stocks is :

$$m_t - p_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(E_t p_{t+1} - p_t) + e_t \quad (1.30A)$$

$$q_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \pi_t + \beta_2(E_t p_{t+1} - p_t) + v_t \quad (1.30B)$$

Where $\alpha_0 > 0$, α_1 , β_1 , $\beta_2 < 0$. If ΔG is the change in the total stock of gold, then the change is estimated at $\theta m_t + (1-\theta) q_t$, where θ is the fraction of the total gold held in gold coins. Relative price [$P_G/P = p_t$] and gold depreciation is a certain fraction of the period's nonmonetary gold demand [$t - 1$], that is q_{t-1} . Therefore the equation (1.29) can be written in linear form as follows:

$$\theta \Delta m_t + (1-\theta)\Delta q_t = \rho_0 + \rho_1 p_t + \rho_2 q_{t-1}$$

$$\Delta m_t + \omega_3 \Delta q_t = \omega_0 + \omega_1 p_t + \omega_2 q_{t-1}$$

$$m_t + \omega_3 q_t = \omega_0 + \omega_1 p_t + (\omega_2 + \omega_3) q_{t-1} + m_{t-1} \quad (1.31)$$

where is the parameter value ω is ρ_1 , $\rho_2 < 0$, $\omega_3 = (1-\theta)/\theta$ and $\omega_i = \rho_i/\theta$. Equality (1.30A), (1.30B) and (1.31) used to find the dynamic solution of p_t , m_t , dan q_t . Equality (1.30A), (1.30B) and (1.31) shows two grace time variables [m_{t-1} dan q_{t-1}] plus two surprises [e_t and v_t]. The solutions to the three equations can be written in reduced-form equations, where all endogenous variables are functions of all exogenous variables:

$$p_t = \phi_{10} + \phi_{11} q_{t-1} + \phi_{12} m_{t-1} + \phi_{13} e_t + \phi_{14} v_t \quad (1.32A)$$

$$m_t = \phi_{20} + \phi_{21} q_{t-1} + \phi_{22} m_{t-1} + \phi_{23} e_t + \phi_{24} v_t \quad (1.32B)$$

$$q_t = \phi_{30} + \phi_{31} q_{t-1} + \phi_{32} m_{t-1} + \phi_{33} e_t + \phi_{34} v_t \quad (1.32C)$$

Evaluation of the value of the coefficient ij can be done by defining price expectations in the period [$t + 1$] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E_t p_{t+1} &= \phi_{10} + \phi_{11} q_t + \phi_{12} m_t \\ &= \phi_{10} + \phi_{11} [\phi_{30} + \phi_{31} q_{t-1} + \phi_{32} m_{t-1} + \phi_{33} e_t + \phi_{34} v_t] \\ &+ \phi_{12} [\phi_{20} + \phi_{21} q_{t-1} + \phi_{22} m_{t-1} + \phi_{23} e_t + \phi_{24} v_t] \end{aligned} \quad (1.33)$$

Substitute (1.33) into (1.30A), (1.30) and (1.31) to replace $[E_t p_{t+1}]$ and the model used includes (1.30A) and (1.30B) but is replaced by the gold accumulation relationship (1.31), namely:

$$m_t + \omega_3 q_t = k \quad (1.34)$$

This means that the total gold stock is constant at k. To analyze the behavior of the price level in the form (1.30A), (1.30B) and (1.34), substitution (1.30A) and (1.30B) to (1.34), namely:

$$p_t + \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 (E_t p_{t+1} - p_t) + e_t + \omega_3 [\beta_0 + \beta_1 p_t + \beta_2 (E_t p_{t+1} - p_t) + v_t] = k \quad (1.35)$$

The bootstrap-free solution is that the price level is determined by random shocks $[e_t]$ and $[v_t]$. The bootstrap-free solution is

$$p_t = \phi_0 + \phi_1 e_t + \phi_2 v_t \quad (1.36)$$

Equality (1.36) shows that the value of $E_t p_{t+1} = \phi_0$. Substitution (1.36) back to (1.35) produce the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & (1 - \alpha_1)[\phi_0 + \phi_1 e_t + \phi_2 v_t] + \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \phi_0 + e_t \\ & + \omega_3 [\beta_0 + (\beta_1 - \beta_2)(\phi_0 + \phi_1 e_t + \phi_2 v_t) + \beta_2 \phi_0 + v_t] = k \\ & (1 - \alpha_1)\phi_1 e_t + e_t + (1 - \alpha_1)\phi_2 v_t + \alpha_0 + \phi_0 + \omega_3 \beta_0 + \omega_3 \beta_1 \phi_0 \\ & + \omega_3 (\beta_1 - \beta_2)[\phi_1 e_t + \phi_2 v_t] + \omega_3 v_t = k \end{aligned} \quad (1.37)$$

Equality (1.36) can be fulfilled with three parameters or coefficient requirements, namely:

1. $\phi_0 + \alpha_0 + \omega_3 \beta_0 + \omega_3 \phi_0 \beta_1 = k$ or $\phi_0 = [k - \alpha_0 - \omega_3 \beta_0] / [1 + \omega_3 \beta_1]$,
2. $(1 - \alpha_1)\phi_1 + 1 + \omega_3 (\beta_1 - \beta_2)\phi_1 = 0$ or $\phi_1 = -1 / [1 - \alpha_1 + \omega_3 (\beta_1 - \beta_2)]$, dan
3. $(1 - \alpha_1)\phi_2 + \omega_3 (\beta_1 - \beta_2)\phi_2 + \omega_3 = 0$ or $\phi_2 = -\omega_3 / [1 - \alpha_1 + \omega_3 (\beta_1 - \beta_2)]$.

Known value $\beta_1 > 0$ and $\beta_2, \alpha_1 < 0$ so that the value $\phi_1, \phi_2 < 0$. Hence the positive surprise on the demand for gold coins $[e_t > 0]$ and a positive surprise on nonmonetary gold demand $[v_t > 0]$ will temporarily lower the general price level. Therefore, an increase in the demand for non-monetary gold and gold coins will lower the general price level. From (1.36) and (1.37) it is shown that the variance of the general price level with the average general price level $[\phi_0]$ is :

$$Var(p_t) = \frac{\sigma_e^2 + \omega_3^2 \sigma_v^2}{[1 - \alpha_1 + \omega_3 (\beta_1 - \beta_2)]^2} \quad (1.38)$$

Where $E(e_t, v_t) = 0$. from (1.38) It is known that the effect of each parameter value results in variations in the general price level. If the value of parameter β_1 1 increases or the elasticity of

demand for non-monetary gold increases, then the volatility of the price level decreases on a surprise demand for non-monetary gold and certain gold coins. Likewise, changes in or the ratio of the gold reserve to the stock of paper money will not affect the volatility of the price level on a fixed gold stock. The general price level solution is substituted into equations (1.30A) and (1.30B) to obtain the dynamics of demand for gold [m_t] and non-monetary gold [q_t], namely:

$$m_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \phi_0 - (1 + \alpha_1) p_t + e_t \quad m_t = -[\phi_1 + \alpha_1 \phi_1 - 1] e_t - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_1 \phi_2) v_t \quad (1.39A)$$

$$q_t = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 - \beta_2) p_t + \beta_2 \phi_0 + v_t$$

$$q_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \phi_0 + (\beta_1 - \beta_2) \phi_1 e_t + [(\beta_1 - \beta_2) \phi_2 + 1] v_t \quad (1.39B)$$

Known value $\beta_1 > 0$, β_2 , $\alpha_1 < 0$ dan ϕ_1 , $\phi_2 < 0$, so a positive surprise on the demand for gold money [$e_t > 0$] and non-monetary gold demand [$v_t > 0$] will temporarily increase the demand for gold and non-monetary gold. On the other hand, a negative surprise on the demand for gold money [$e_t < 0$] dan permintaan emas nonmoneter [$v_t < 0$] will temporarily reduce the demand for gold and non-monetary gold demand.

Based on the relationship between the variables, the conceptual framework used in this study is as follows:

Figure 2.1: conceptual framework (ARDL Panel): Optimization of monetary policy and fiscal policy in controlling economic stability at the level of Inflation and Economic Growth

Hypothesis

The hypothesis is a provisional assumption or perception whose truth still needs to be tested empirically. The hypothesis in this study is that Monetary and Fiscal Policy (Crowding Out and Time Lag) can optimize the level of Economic Growth and Inflation of the Nine Country Of Asia Pacific Economic Corporation (Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia). , Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Mexico, Chile, Peru.

III. METHOD

This research was conducted on the nine countries of the Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation, namely, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Mexico, Chile, Peru. The time series data used in this study is time series data from 2009-2019. Because the data in this study is secondary data, the researchers obtained data through a second party or source, namely the World Bank. <http://www.worldbank.org>, International Monetary Fund. <http://www.imf.org> and CEIC. <http://www.ceicdata.com>.

The data analysis techniques used are four quantitative analysis methods, namely the Siimingl method, the ARDL panel method.

$$INF_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

The following is the regression panel formula by country:

$$INF_{Indonesiat} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

$$INF_{Jepangt} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

$$INF_{Malaysiat} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

$$INF_{Filipinat} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

$$INF_{Singaporet} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

$$INF_{Thailandt} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

$$INF_{Mexicot} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

$$INF_{Chilet} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

$$INF_{Perut} = \alpha + \beta_1 PDB_{it} + \beta_2 INV_{it} + \beta_3 GOV_{it} + \beta_4 KURS_{it} + e$$

IV. DISCUSSION

ARDL Panel Discussion

Based on the overall results, it is known that in the long term the significant ones that affect economic growth are INF, INV, GOV, EXCHANGE which affect GDP. The following table summarizes the results of the ardl panel:

Tabel 4.1 : Rangkuman Panel ARDL

Variable	Indonesia	Japan	Malaysia	Filiphina	Singapore	Thailand	Mexico	Chile	Peru	Short Run	Long Run
INF	I	0	0	I	0	I	I	I	0	I	I
INV	I	I	I	I	I	I	I	I	0	I	1
GOV	I	0	0	I	0	I	0	I	0	0	0
KURS	I	I	0	I	0	I	I	I	0	I	0

Figure 4.1: Time Stability of Economic Growth Control

Nine Country Of Asia Pasific Economic Cooperation

It can be seen that the leading indicators for controlling economic growth in the Nine Countries of Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation in dealing with economic growth in each country are experiencing the same thing. The results of the research above are similar to the studies that have been summarized, namely the study of Shumpeter, in Putong (2010) that economic growth is an increase in output (national income) caused by a natural increase in the rate of population growth and the rate of savings (Yan et al., 2020). There are three main factors or components of economic growth, namely capital accumulation, population growth, and matters related to an increase in the number of the workforce which are considered to positively stimulate economic growth (Rahman et al., 2019) (Papadamou et al 2020).

According to (Subandi, 2012) the inflation rate is an indicator of a country's economic stability. The rise and fall of the inflation rate reflects the economic turmoil of a country. A high inflation rate is certainly very detrimental to the State (Okhunjanov, B. B. 2020) (N., Davis et al, 2020). Experience shows that in the third world, favorable (bad) economic conditions have spurred high inflation rates and in turn will be disastrous for low-income people.

According to (Hussain and Haque, 2016) foreign investment plays an important role in the economic growth of developing countries. It affects the scenario of employment, production, prices, import income, exports, general welfare of the receiving country and the balance of payments and serves as one of the important sources of economic growth (Amstad et al, 2020).

According to (Solikin, 2018) there are two different views related to the relationship between government spending and economic growth in macroeconomic theory (Zhang, Q. 2020) (Adenomon et al, 2020). First, according to Adolf Wagner, the amount of government spending is influenced by economic development, meaning that the more advanced an economy the size of the government will also be seen from government spending. Second, according to Keynes's theory, government spending will affect the economy.

According to Pridayanti, (2013), in this case, international trade activities are largely determined by the currency exchange rate of the country concerned. For example, the exchange rate increases (appreciation) the price of export goods from Indonesia is relatively cheaper in the US, so exports will increase. Conversely, if the exchange rate weakens (depreciates) the price of goods from the US is relatively more expensive so that imports will tend to decline which will affect the trade performance and economic growth of a country.

In controlling economic stability, the Crowding Out and Time Lag framework is followed by an approach based on investment, government spending and exchange rates. Fiscal policy (Crowding Out) can have an optimal effect in overcoming economic growth through investment and government spending. Meanwhile, monetary policy (Time Lag) can have an optimal effect in overcoming the inflation rate through the exchange rate.

Panel

From the panel, it turns out that INF, INV and GOV GDP are also able to become leading indicators for controlling the countries of Indonesia, the Philippines, Thailand and Chile. The results of the study (Warjiyo and Juhro, 2016) state that low and controlled inflation is a requirement for sustainable economic growth. According to the theory of endogenous growth, economies of scale, increasing returns of scale and technology play an important role in output growth. In this theory, output growth is highly dependent on the variable rate of return on capital. Variables such as inflation can reduce the rate of return on capital so that it will reduce capital accumulation in the end suppressing output.

V. CONCLUSION

From a GDP panel, inflation, investment, government spending and exchange rates are the leading indicators (Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Mexico, Chile and Peru). However, its position is unstable in the short run and long run. The main leading indicators are optimizing variables in controlling economic stability in the Nine Country Of Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation, namely, GDP, inflation, investment, government spending and exchange rates seen from the short run and long run stability, where GDP, inflation, and investment and government spending and exchange rate variables in the long and short term significantly control economic stability. This research is the same as (Yahya et al., 2021) investment expenditures related to the management of resources available at this time in order to be used or benefited in the future. The output gap is defined as the percentage difference between actual output and potential output (Mishkin, 2017).

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